

Remember/regeneration treatment method as a new holistic approach in patients with alopecia totalis: A case report

Alopecia totalisli hastalarda yeni bir bütüncü yaklaşım olarak hatırlatma/rejenerasyon tedavisi metodu: Bir vaka sunumu

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ABSTRACT

Background: Alopecia areata (AA) is an autoimmune disorder which is characterized with destruction of hair follicles. The disease manifests with patches of nonscarring in scalp or other hairy skin areas in varying severity clinically. The Remember/Regeneration Therapy Method (RTM) is a novel holistic medicine approach that targets physiopathological changes in quadruplet body structures, and includes various complementary methods such as acupuncture, ozone therapy and phytotherapy, etc. in different combinations which are determined depending on affected diseases. **Case Report:** We present a case with alopecia totalis were successfully healed with the RTM therapy without a significant side effects. **Conclusion:** RTM may provide consistent results for alopecia and similar many autoimmune diseases by using combinations of various holistic medicine methods in different doses, durations and sessions. The identification of epigenetically regulated genes related with autoimmune alopecia may be promising in order to develop epigenetic drugs for disease management.

ÖZ

Arka plan: Alopesi areata (AA), saç foliküllerinin destrüksiyonu ile karakterize otoimmün bir hastalıktır. Hastalık, klinik olarak değişen şiddette saçlı deride veya diğer kıllı cilt bölgelerinde iz bırakmayan yamalar ile kendini gösterir. Hatırlatma/Rejenerasyon Terapi Yöntemi (RTM), dördüz vücut yapılarındaki fizyopatolojik değişiklikleri hedefleyen, akupunktur, ozon tedavisi ve fitoterapi gibi çeşitli tamamlayıcı yöntemleri, etkilenen hastalıklara göre belirlenen farklı kombinasyonlarda içeren yeni bir bütüncül tıp yaklaşımıdır. **Olgu Sunumu:** RTM tedavisi ile önemli bir yan etki olmaksızın başarıyla iyileşen alopesi universalisli bir olguyu sunuyoruz. **Sonuç:** RTM, çeşitli holistik tıp yöntemlerinin farklı doz, süre ve seanslarda kombinasyonları kullanılarak alopesi ve benzeri birçok otoimmün hastalık için faydalı sonuçlar sağlayabilir. İlerleyen süreçte, otoimmün alopesi ile ilgili epigenetik olarak düzenlenmiş genlerin tanımlanması, hastalıkların tedavisi için epigenetik ilaçlar geliştirmek için umut verici olabilir.

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Anahtar Kelimeler: Alopecia Totalis, Otoimmün Hastalıklar, RTM, Bütüncül Tıp, Epigenetik

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INTRODUCTION

Alopecia areata (AA) is an autoimmune disorder which is characterized with inflammatory destruction of hair follicles via cytotoxic T-lymphocytes reacting with follicular autoantigens and eventually hair loss. The disease manifests with patches of nonscarring in scalp or other hairy skin areas, and exhibits clinical variability in severity. While alopecia focalis (AF) is in the form of patchy hair loss on the scalp, alopecia totalis (AT) is the loss of all scalp hair. Alopecia universalis (AU) is characterized by the loss of hair all over the body (1). Although spontaneous amelioration occurs in %80 of patients within first year of the disease which is showing unpredictable onset and progression, the disease can

relapse or progress to alopecia totalis and universalis at any stage (2).

While the cause of alopecia areata is not understood completely, various factors such as psychologic stress, microbiota, pathogens immune checkpoint inhibitors on the basis of genetic predisposition are confirmed as the most important contributors (3).

To date, various therapies including topical immunotherapy, steroids, photodynamic therapy, immunosuppressive agents, TNF α inhibitors, and other therapies, such as sulfasalazine, bexarotene, JAK inhibitors, and simvastatin/ezetimibe have been used in order to treat AT/AU. Although some of abovementioned modalities showed significant efficacy against hair

loss, none of these treatments provide amelioration completely (4).

The Remember/Regeneration Therapy Method (RTM) is a holistic approach which consists of diagnostic and treatment systems that include mainly phytotherapy and different combinations of various complementary and traditional medical methods such as acupuncture, cupping therapy, hirudotherapy, ozone therapy, etc. While various phytotherapeutic combinations form the basis of the RTM, the other treatment modalities are used in order to support effect of the phytotherapy. Moreover, phytotherapeutic applications of RTM are classified under two main groups of phytotherapeutics called as “Remember/Reminder Herbs” and “Regeneration Herbs” which consist of different amounts of various medical herbs. On the other hand, according to the RTM model, diseases are seen as the reflection of epigenetic changes in the phenotype resulting from the gene-environment mismatch. The treatment strategy is based on the recovery of health by essentially improving the deteriorating structures. It has been considered that pathological process of a disease can potentially be reversed by the RTM, considering the epigenetic changes. It has been clinically observed that epigenetic changes and irregularities improved when appropriate treatment protocols were applied, as in the RTM model (5).

In this case report, we present an ameliorated alopecia totalis case due to the RTM phytotherapeutics clinically. The case was followed up periodically for 5 years in order to show that the RTM provided a cure almost. Possible mechanisms of effect of the RTM and the recovery process of a patients with alopecia after the beginning of the RTM will be discussed.

CASE REPORT

An 8-year-old male patient was suffering from AA when he applied to our clinic first time. Although the disease onseted as A, after 2 years it turned into AT via loss of hair completely. There is no family story and any stress factor which trigger the disease. The case was cured with RTM phytotherapeutics consists of different herbal extracts. Various RTM phytotherapeutics shown in the table were used for the case to date. (Table 1)

FOLLOW UP PERIOD AND THE DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS

The patient was called periodically in order to be followed up, and physical examination and other practices were performed. Photographs of the patient's recovery were taken during the follow-up period and

arranged for comparison of improvement over the years. Briefly, the patient's complaints started to decrease within months and the patient was healed completely in four years almost. Any adverse effect due to RTM were not detected. The patient's treatment is still continuing. The photos which is showing the amelioration includes 5 years of treatment interval to date (Figures 1-6).

LIMITATIONS

In this study, we could not use molecular methods to explain the mechanism of action of RTM in terms of epigenetic regulation. Since the case was out of control of our clinic before RTM treatment, they applied to us without epigenetic analysis. Therefore, we could not show the possible mechanism about epigenetic process. The fact that the study was a retrospective study also contributed to this deficiency.

DISCUSSION

Novel scientific discoveries in the sciences of biology and genetic have demonstrated that inheritance has a whole new dimension beyond the genes, not in the structure of the DNA. In this new dimension of inheritance called epigenetics, it has been shown that changes can be transferred to new generations (6,7). The importance of epigenetic modifications in long-term memory performance has been demonstrated in the most extensive and comprehensive study on DNA methylation. The processes such as chromatin remodeling, histone modifications, and non-coding RNA are also other important changes that belong to epigenetic mechanisms (8).

Autoimmun reactions often result from defects in immune tolerance that result in the formation and proliferation of autoreactive T cells and autoantibodies (9,10). Besides DNA methylation, histone modifications, another epigenetic mechanism, are highly dynamic and are regulated by “writer” and “eraser” enzymes (11). Histone modifications have been shown to play a role in autoimmune diseases by modulating immune tolerance (12,13). As promising treatment strategies, some small-molecule inhibitors targeting histone-modifying enzymes also provide new treatment options for diseases such as cancers and autoimmune diseases (14). In addition to these drugs that work at molecular levels, many phytochemicals have been shown to be effective on certain conditions such as cancer chemoprevention and metabolic syndrome through epigenetic regulation (15,16).

The RTM is a holistic medicine that describes the anatomical and physiological aspects of physiopathological changes in quadruplet body

Table 1. Dose alterations in medical applications and phytotherapeutics forming the RTM protocol

Alterations of RTM Treatment Protocols by Years			
Treatment Period (Year)	Other Treatment Modalities and Doses	Daily Doses Phytotherapeutics and Orders in the Year	
		Order I	Order II
2017	2 sessions minor ozone therapy 2 sessions magneto therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-KBRT, 3X3 • ISY-CP, 3X3 • DVD-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 3X1 	
2018	2 sessions minor ozone therapy 2 sessions magneto therapy 1 session cupping therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-KBRT, 3X3 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 3X1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X3 • ISY-CP, 3X3 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 3X1
2019	2 sessions minor ozone therapy 2 sessions magneto therapy 2 session cupping therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X3 • ISY-CP, 3X3 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 3X1 • REGULIN, 3x1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X1 • ISY-CP, 3X3 • IST-ARD, 2X1 • SDS-X, 3X1 • Milk Thistle Seed Oil, 2x2 tea spoon
2020	3 sessions minor ozone therapy 2 sessions major ozone therapy 2 sessions magneto therapy 2 session cupping therapy 1 session intradermal ozone therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X1 • ISY-CP, 3X1 • IST-ARD, 2X1 • KT-REM, 3X1 • SDS-X, 3X1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 2X1 • ISY-CP, 2X1 • IST-ARD, 2X1 • KT-REM, 2X1 • SDS-X, 2X1
2021	6 sessions minor ozone therapy 6 sessions major ozone therapy 4 sessions magneto therapy 2 sessions cupping therapy 4 sessions laser therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X2 • ISY-CP, 2X1 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 2X1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-KBRT, 3X3 • ISY-CP, 2X1 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 2X1
2022	2 sessions minor ozone therapy 2 sessions major ozone therapy 2 sessions magneto therapy 1 session intradermal ozone therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X3 • ISY-CP, 3X3 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 2X1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVD-ADÇ, 3X2 • ISY-CP, 3X2 • IST-ARD, 3X1 • SDS-X, 2X1 • REGULIN, 3X1

Figures 1-6. Photos showing the amelioration of the cases by years

Figures 1-6. Photos showing the amelioration of the cases by years

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structures (QBSs). The RTM phytotherapeutics which consist of a unique mixture of different herbal ingredients in different proportions, and they placed the center of the RTM. Also, when it is need, many complementary medical methods such as acupuncture, ozone therapy, cupping therapy, hirudotherapy, etc. may add to the RTM phytotherapeutics that is major axis of the model. In the RTM, diseases are seen as the reflection of epigenetic changes in the phenotype resulting from the gene-environment mismatch. The treatment strategy is based on the recovery of health by essentially improving the deteriorating structures. Considering that many of the epigenetic changes which lead to disease can potentially be reversed, it has been clinically observed that epigenetic changes and irregularities improved with appropriate treatment protocols were applied, as in the RTM. Thus, firstly, these extraordinary and abnormal conditions that leads to the gene-environment mismatch should be eliminated, and secondly, previous normal physiological processes should be reminded to body. Already, the name of RTM comes from the special treatment strategy that compose of proper combinations of regenerative and reminder phytotherapeutic agents and holistic medicine methods (5).

In current case, the patient's complaints were significantly decreased by our treatment model. It is more likely that the efficacy on all parameters is related to possible smart molecules which regulates epigenetic modification found in RTM phytotherapeutics.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, The RTM treatment was well tolerated by the patient with AU, and no side effects were observed. The identification of epigenetically regulated genes related to AU may be promising in order to develop epigenetic drugs for disease management. However, further functional studies might be required to determine epigenetically regulated genes in autoimmune diseases such as AA and AU.

Declaration of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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